

matlab code	figure name	paper figure number	figure topic	data included
HYCOMc004_plot_N2_Ueig_z_01.m	Nz_Ueig_prof_so.png		1 eigenfunctions	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_resolution_05.m	wavelength_K1M2M3M4_v4.png		2 mode 1 wave lengths	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_modes_specflux_03.m	specKE_tukey02_remslope_newfreq_modes_r300_D1-D2-HH_v4.png		3 KE for modes and frequencies	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_modes_specflux_03.m	specflux_tukey02_remslope_newfreq_modes_r300_D1-D2-HH_v4.png		4 Flux for modes and frequencies	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_modes_specflux_03.m	KE_APE_rat_zonave_tukey02_remslope_newfreq_modes_r300_v2.png		5 zonally averaged KE and APE	1
Hc004_read_points_modes_01.m	fftpoints_modes_tkwin0.2_nwin3_noprewhit.png		6 KE spectra	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_modes_specflux_03.m	D3_D4_ratioHH_tukey02_remslope_newfreq_r300_v2.png		7 KE for D3 and D4	1
Hc004_ssh_k_omega_spec_v2.m	k_om_spectra_3areas_m_v2.png		8 omega-k spectra	1
HYCOMc004_read_global_resolution_05.m	zonave_K1M2M4HZ_VER_res.png		9 modes resolved	0
HYCOMc004_read_global_modes_specflux_03.m	D3_D4_ratio_D1_D2_tukey02_remslope_newfreq_r300_v2.png		10 supertidal to tidal KE ratio	1

fortran code	launch file	purpose
extract_vars_c004_v14.f	extract_vars_190.com	tile the global .a files and create 4D time series
mean_T_S_thknss_c004_v1.f	mean_T_S_thknss_191.com	mean T and S and thickness
mean_Nlayr_c004_v1.f	mean_Nlayr_190.com	compute buoyancy frequency
WEIG_layr_c004_v1.f	WEIG_layr_190.com	solve Sturm Liouville eq
filter_modes_layr_c004_v1.f	fit_modes_layr_190.com	fit eigenfunctions to compute modal amplitudes
spec_energyflux_c004_v1.f	spec_energyflux_190.com	compute KE, APE, fluxes for several frequency bands
PDENS.f		fft library files
FREQFFT.f		fft library files
FFT.f		fft library files
note: codes that combine the tiles have been omitted		